

EVIDENCE-BASED TOXICOLOGY
An open science journal for environmental health research

Evaluation Report (triage round 1) for **TEBT-2024-0007**

Submission Information Table

Submission Title	Spent coffee ground cubes as a novel biosorbent for dye remediation
Submission Reference	TEBT-2024-0007
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley ORCID 0000-0003-4021-0785
Number of Reviewers	1 (the handling editor)
Submission Type	Single-Stage Study ▾
Preprint DOI	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11107119
Status	In Editorial Review ▾
Evaluation Date	5 Jun 2024
Evaluation Round	Triage round 1
Recommendation	Revise ▾
Handling Editor's Explanation for Recommendation	This manuscript shows promise. Revision before peer-review will allow the peer-review process to focus on substantive methodological issues rather than structural ones, increasing its value for both the reviewers and the submitting authors.

Summary of article and editor recommendations

This is a promising manuscript. However, the way it is currently structured presents some challenges to following the study's objectives and the methods. Experimental detail could also be further developed to support the reproducibility of the authors' work. In developing their submission, the authors could consider clearly delineating each individual objective of the study, then restructuring the manuscript to carefully separate the description of these objectives from the methods, and the methods from the results. Precisely characterising each individual objective provides a framework under which each methodological component of the study can be introduced and clearly related back to a specific study goal.

Checklist of minimum required information

Y = Yes | N = No | X = Not Applicable

Present	Item checked
N -	Preprint, relevant revision materials, and supplemental material available on Zenodo
Y -	Full name, affiliations, and ORCIDiDs (if available) of each author are present
N -	Structured abstract has been provided
Y -	Author contributions in the form of a CRediT statement have been given
Y -	Complete funding details are given, or "no funding" is declared
Y -	An informative disclosure of interests for all authors has been provided, or disclosure declined
Y -	3rd-party data and program code are fully cited, if relevant (TOP 1, level 3)
N -	Data and code availability has been stated and links to both are functional
X -	One or more appropriate reporting checklists for submission type have been completed
N -	Supplemental materials have plain English file names

Comments about minimum required information

1. The abstract should be structured, i.e. presented in terms of context, objective, methods, results.
2. Absence of conflicts of interest has been declared. At EBT we do encourage authors to complete a structured declaration of financial and non-financial interests. The template

we offer (recommended but not required) is [here](#), with an example of a completed declaration [here](#).

3. The DOI link to the data on figshare is broken and should be checked. (I'm afraid I couldn't find a matching dataset by directly searching on figshare for the reference numbers either.)
4. In the next version of the preprint, please add line numbering to facilitate review.
5. While I appreciate that there is no reporting template for this type of study design, I can recommend (and the authors should bear with me here!) the use of the [JARS checklist for quantitative research](#). Obviously there are several parts of the checklist that require interpretation for the authors' study (e.g. experimental manipulation will not be psychological, of course) or just are not relevant (e.g. demographic characteristics), but as an overall structure it is probably 80% applicable or better.

Structured Evaluation

KEY: R = Revisions recommended. N = No issues identified at this time. X = Not applicable.

Domain	1. Objectives, context, and mode of research
Compliance	Important issues identified - that should be addressed prior to peer-review -
Specific Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> R - Clarity about knowledge goals or hypotheses of the research (e.g. PECO) R - Justification for conducting the research (context, rationale) R - Differentiation between research in confirmatory or exploratory mode R - Other (please explain in comments)
Comments	<p>1. The objective (“we report on the removal of EB dye by sustainably produced quaternized cubes and compare their performance to un-quaternized SCG cubes”) is somewhat buried in the final paragraph of the introduction, and does not seem to capture the full extent of the knowledge goals of the study - these are various and nuanced, and sold somewhat short by the introduction.</p> <p>I would suggest giving the objective its own paragraph and making really clear what the research goals of the study are, possibly in a numbered list if appropriate. If I understand correctly these are at least about: (a) testing in a laboratory environment the ability of quaternized SCGs to remove EB dye; (b) comparing the performance of quaternized vs. unquaternized SCGs; and I notice that in the results (section 3.1) there are further objectives to test the “effect of (c) roast level and (d) particle size on dye adsorption”. There are also some objectives implied by the choices of subheadings in the results and discussion section, e.g. “cube composition affects adsorption”.</p> <p>Clearly stating the various objectives and related methodological components of the</p>

	<p>study will help with structuring the methods and results sections of the manuscript, in turn making it easier for reviewers to evaluate the validity of the methods for each component. While doing this, the authors should also make clearer what they are testing in relation to the hypotheses of the study (the primary goals of the study in relation to e.g. any null hypotheses) vs. what in their approach is exploratory (as might relate to e.g. effect modifiers or other factors it may not be possible to test in this study but might be tested in follow-up work).</p> <p>2. For our audience, it might be worth explaining in a little more detail what quaternization is and why it is of interest in this study. In general, the issues raised in the discussion that seem to help contextualise the choices made in designing this study might be better moved to the introduction (this would also address comment 1 from domain 2 below).</p> <p>3. I recommend removing language such as “<i>sustainably</i> produced quaternized cubes” - the study is not really providing evidence for environmental impact (though I recognise that potential for reduction in environmental impact is part of the context of the study). The authors could instead claim that the quaternized cubes <i>may</i> be more sustainable, or make it clear that the sustainability component is a motivator for the study or is the authors opinion, but it should not be presented as fact unless there is citable evidence to directly support this statement. Being very deliberate about this may also help simplify the discussion (see comments in domain 3 below), if there is clear daylight between the goals of the study (experimental work on SCG cubes) and the broader environmental case for their use (perhaps better suited to a separate review or commentary).</p>
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Domain	2. Soundness and rigour of experimental approach
Compliance	Important issues identified ▾ that should be addressed prior to peer-review ▾
Specific Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> R ▾ Theory as to how the experiment delivers the knowledge goal R ▾ Identification and authentication of experimental components R ▾ Approach to power and replicates R ▾ Bias controls: e.g. randomisation, masking, complete data, training, etc. X ▾ Other (please explain in comments)
Comments	<p>1. I think we are missing information from e.g. step 2.2 as to why the grounds were prepared in the way they were? In general, the manuscript would benefit from more (perhaps quite a lot more) discussion of why the experiment has been set up the way it has. There are elements of this in the discussion section that could be moved to context or method, depending on the focus.</p> <p>2. At the moment, it is difficult to answer triage questions about soundness and rigour of approach because of the structural issues with the paper. When restructuring, the authors should also be alert to issues such as power and replicates (for example, I am not currently sure what the group sizes are for each experiment, or how many times the experiment was run), any bias controls they implement (e.g. masking of group assignment), and so forth, and in general make</p>

	sure sufficient information is provided to allow the reader to develop a full understanding of the methods used.
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Domain	3. Analysis of data and reporting of results
Compliance	Important issues identified - that should be addressed prior to peer-review -
Specific Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> X - Data normalisation and cleansing techniques R - Analysis pipeline (qualitative, narrative, and/or statistical methods) R - Summarisation and visualisation of results R - Selectivity in use of data or emphasis on study results X - Other (please explain in comments)
Comments	<p>1. As a general comment, the results are presented narratively in a way that, as currently structured, is challenging to relate back to the objectives of the study. Partly this is because the objectives themselves are not yet as clearly delineated as they could be.</p> <p>2. Specifically in relation to presentation of results, I would suggest (a) clearly presenting the data and analysis for each objective of the study so we can see the quantitative results, then (b) interpreting the quantitative results in narrative text. The structure of the results (and following discussion) should reflect the structure of the objectives, with subheadings for each objective if appropriate.</p> <p>3. The discussion section is quite lengthy and goes some way beyond what is directly studied in the experiments described in the manuscript. It seems to be acting more as a review of the potential application of SCGs than a discussion of the study itself. In the interests of brevity, it might be better to build up the objectives and methods sections with information that supports contextualisation and reproducibility of the study, and worry less about the discussion of the sustainability and likely performance of the method in the wild - it is a laboratory study, and it is perfectly fine to present it as such.</p>

Domain	4. Transparency and reproducibility
Compliance	Important issues identified - that should be addressed prior to peer-review -
Specific Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> N - Citation of data, program code, and methods (TOP 1 - L3)* R - Provision of code, data, and materials for replication (TOP 2,3,4 - L2) X - Appropriateness and/or implementation of reporting checklist (TOP 5 - L3) R - Description of preregistered methods and/or analysis plan (TOP 6,7 - L2) X - Adherence to preregistered methods and/or analysis plan (TOP 6,7 - L2) X - Other (please explain in comments) <p>*Parentheses indicate EBT's implementation of TOP guidelines. More information here.</p>
Comments	1. I think there is information missing about e.g. the dimensions, density, porosity,

	<p>and other characteristics of the cubes so we understand more about their nature as the intervention in this study? If someone were to follow up on this study, they would want to know if they were creating similar cubes, for example. In relation to this, some figures about e.g. what the cubes look like, the experimental set-up described briefly in section 2.5, would also be helpful in understanding exactly what the authors did in this study.</p> <p>2. Information about methods is often intermixed with other sections. For example, the last paragraph of the introduction includes information about how the spent coffee ground cubes are created, which may be better situated in the methods section. More importantly, the first paragraph of the results (section 3.1) has information not only about methods, but also about the objectives of the study (determining the effect of roast level and particle size on dye absorption). The last section of paragraph 3.1 introduces SEM as a method for exploring why there might be similarities or differences between the performance of the difference cubes, which would also be better presented in the methods.</p> <p>This should be untangled to help the reader to follow the goals of the study, and how the goals were delivered by the experimental set-up and analysis of collected data. The experimental groups in the study all need to be described in detail in the methods section.</p> <p>3. It is hard to tell without access to the data on figshare, but I feel there may not be sufficient data presented to allow the reader to follow derivation of results or conduct their own analyses, to explore the data themselves or reproduce the authors findings. More tables in the manuscript showing the data from which figures are derived, and clarity about the data from which the figures are generated, would be welcome.</p> <p>4. The authors should make it clear this study was not preregistered, so it is not ambiguous (unless I missed this in the text).</p>
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Domain	5. Ethics and interests
Compliance	Moderate to minor issues identified - that may be addressed after peer-review -
Specific Issues	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> R - Informativeness of declarations of interests</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> N - Ethical approval for research with human or animal material or participants</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> X - Other (please explain in comments)</p>
Comments	<p>1. I don't see any issues relating to ethics and interests, though as indicated above some more information about non-financial interests might help the reader situate the research in the authors' motivations - for example, are the authors working more generally on SCGs as part of a broader programme of work relating to improving the environmental performance of remediation strategies? It is only contextual information so not critical, but it is nice to have.</p>